

A COMPARISON OF CARE RENDERED BY ED PHYSICIANS WITH VARYING MEDICAL BACKGROUNDS

Citation. Lewis LM, Heston TF, Rush C. A comparison of care rendered by ED physicians with varying medical backgrounds. [South Med J 1990;83\(9\):2S-19](#). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8229711

Abstract. This prospective study compared the quality of the history (Hx), physical examination (PE), diagnosis, and treatment (Tx) of patients with hand injuries as performed by emergency department (ED) physicians with varying training backgrounds. There were 465 cases reported by 93 physicians. No differences between residency-trained and legacy practice-track EM board-certified physicians were found. Physicians of lesser training were found to be more meticulous about documenting history and following tetanus protocols, but they ordered more tests and were less likely to perform or document adequate treatment.

This research was conducted with the St. Louis Emergency Physicians' Association Research Group. The following year we published data collected throughout St. Louis showing a gender bias in evaluating acute chest pain in the emergency department (1).

References

1. Heston, Thomas F. and Lewis, Lawrence M. Gender bias in the evaluation and management of acute nontraumatic chest pain. The St. Louis Emergency Physicians' Association Research Group. *Fam Pract Res J.* 1992 Dec;12(4):383-9.